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Abstract	<p>The common European Green Deal data space will interconnect currently fragmented and dispersed data from various sources (including in-situ, statistical, cartographical and remote sensing), both for/from the private and public sectors, to support the objectives of the European Green Deal. It will offer an interoperable, trusted IT environment for data processing, and a set of rules of legislative, administrative and contractual nature that determine the rights of access to and use of the data.</p> <p>This document is the Deliverable 2.1 for the AD4GD project. It presents the initial results achieved in the context of Task 2.1 "Identification of the in-situ networks contributing to the Green Deal data" as part of Work Package 2 "In-situ networks, CitSci and Socioeconomic Data". The reader should consider that a more elaborated version of this document will be released on month 20 the project as Deliverable 2.2.</p> <p>The document provides an overview of the identified in-situ data sources and their relations with the Essential Variables (EVs) as a basis for a common semantic framework to better integrate heterogeneous in-situ data sources into the Green Deal Data Space (GDDS) following the FAIR principles. The implementation of FAIR can be completed by one or more nodes that will be dedicated devoted to data discovery and finding information: nodes of the OGC Web Coverage Service (and the OGC API Coverages) for data access of a subset of</p>
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	<p>the coverage data; nodes implementing the OGC Web Feature Service (and the OGC API Features) for data access of a subset of the feature data collections; nodes implementing OGC Sensor Observation Service (or the OGC Sensor Things API) for data access of a subset of the observations and measurements; and a OGC definition service with a vocabulary of observedProperties. Another important component of interoperability and trust is the need for providing the data provenance and the data quality information. Another aspect of trust is to provide authentication and authorization with OpenID Connect, certificates and HTTPS can be used to ensure that services are genuine and have not been tampered with. For this, we should adopt solutions coming from the IT mainstream.</p>
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ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
API	Application Programming Interface
CitSci	Citizen Science
DMP	Data Management Principles
ENEON	European Network of Earth Observation Networks
ENVRI	Environmental Research Infrastructures
EPOS	European Plate Observing System
ESDAC	European Soil Data Centre
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GDDS	Green Deal Data Space
GEO	Group on Earth Observations
GUF	Geospatial User Feedback
HVD	High Value Datasets
INSPIRE	Infrastructure for Spatial Information in Europe
IDSA	International Data Spaces Association
IoT	Internet of Things
PID	Permanent Identifier
RI s	Research Infrastructures
R&I	Research and Innovation
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
STA	Sensor Thing API
TRUST	Transparency, Responsibility, User focus, Sustainability, and Technology

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The common European Green Deal data space will interconnect currently fragmented and dispersed data from various sources (including in-situ, statistical, cartographical and remote sensing), both for/from the private and public sectors, to support the objectives of the European Green Deal. It will offer an interoperable, trusted IT environment for data processing, and a set of rules of legislative, administrative and contractual nature that determine the rights of access to and use of the data.

The main networks of Earth Observation (e.g. research infrastructures) are recorded in the ENEON graph focused on the essential component of the in-situ measurements and networks, evolving thus to a convenient platform to analyse the Essential Variables in Earth Observation, their relations with the in-situ networks and their role to monitor SDGs. The ENEON data model defines mainly 5 classes of resources, 3 of them relevant for this project: an essential variable, an essential variable product (defined by its requirements), and the Earth Observation network (and its supporting projects). In order to be useful for AD4GD, the original graph needs to be updated and extended beyond research infrastructures. Other in-situ data providers in Europe that can be relevant for the GDDS should be considered, such as INSPIRE, socioeconomic data providers, the environmental agencies and Citizen Science projects. The datasets from the citizen science aggregation portals can become interesting providers to the Green Deal Data Space. However, aggregation portals have some dynamics (some new appear every year while others are abandoned). We propose to create a reduced number of nodes that centralises the access to all citizen science datasets that can be relevant to the GDDS.

Essential Variables are an abstract concept that is commonly associated with a set of measurements (e.g. for the Climatic set there are the Essential Climate Variables). Each set of EVs is classified in themes (e.g. Atmosphere, Land, Ocean) and has several individual variables in it. The EV framework and its EV products provide an excellent starting point to define a set of common concepts that can be used both in remote sensing and in-situ data (including Citizen Science). This gives us a way to semantically classify datasets as EV products independently of the technology and technique used to capture them (in-situ, remote sensing, etc). In practice, this is possible if the EVs and the EV products receive a global and unique identifier. One possible approach is to use a different URI for each one. However, there are some community recognized ontologies of EV and its products that can be reused. Meanwhile, the ENEON graph provides a solution for the ontology that could be used in the GDDS. If the data is not semantically tagged by the use of EV vocabularies it will be almost impossible to aggregate or select the right data e.g. as input for a numerical model in an automatic way in the GDDS. Only a few of the OGC standards and APIs provide a clean way to connect data with the described EV via URIs. Except for the case of the Sensor Thing API (STA), there is a need to extend the OGC Web APIs references to variable definitions.

The implementation of FAIR principles, complemented by other relevant principles (e.g., TRUST and GEO) should be achieved in the GDDS. The principles emphasise machine-actionability (i.e., the capacity of computational systems to find, access, interoperate, and reuse data with none or minimal human intervention) because humans increasingly rely on computational support to deal with data as a result of the increase in volume, complexity, and creation speed of data. It is expected that the GDDS will have one or more nodes that will be dedicated to data discovery and finding information. There are 3 main data models that will result in a number of data access nodes: the OGC Web Coverage Service (and the OGC API Coverages) for coverage data; the OGC Web Feature Service (and the OGC API Features) for feature data collections; the OGC Sensor Observation Service (or the OGC Sensor Things API) for observations and measurements. Most of these nodes should be maintained by the data providers themselves so each provider will have a node in the GDDS. The OGC definition service is proposed as another node that gives access to a vocabulary repository for observedProperties. It should contain a list of EV and its products and other extended vocabularies of variables that the GDDS participants could reuse and point from the data that is being included in the data space, to enable the automatic connection of related dataset. Another component of interoperability and trust is the provenance and the data quality of the data captured in the

metadata catalogue. These aspects are reasonably covered by the ISO 19115-1 and the ISO19157 standards respectively. While most of the data in the GDDS should remain open, it could be beneficial to have controlled access to sensitive data and private data when needed. Another issue in the GDDS is the need for trust that the data and the services are originated and curated by recognized and validated institutions. Nodes implementing OpenID Connect and certificates and HTTPS can be incorporated to ensure that services are genuine and have not been tampered with. These aspects are covered by solutions coming from the IT mainstream.

Figure 1 represents a diagram of a draft architecture that combines ideas from the International Data Spaces Association (IDSA) for authentication authorization, certification and logging and our own views on how the GDDS data space can be deployed.

Figure 1: Draft architecture combining IDSA general IT concept with our views on Geospatial components.

1 INTRODUCTION

Environmental pressures play an important role in the most critical global challenges that humanity faces today (including those related to sustainable energy and food production, water supply, human health and well-being). The mitigation and adaptation to climate change, prevention of environmental pollution, conservation and sustainable use of key natural resources and ecosystem services are vital. Modern society is progressively vulnerable to the increased frequency of natural hazards (such as extreme weather, earthquakes, floods, hunger due to failed harvests or pandemic disease outbreaks) causing loss of life and having an enormous impact on society, and environmental catastrophes can shutter societal security and cause migration with related security problems. In the context of all this problematics, the European Union has adopted the European Green Deal as a way to transform the EU into a modern, resource-efficient and competitive economy, while respecting the boundaries of sustainability and ensuring: no net emissions of greenhouse gases by 2050, economic growth decoupled from resource use, no person and no place left behind. The European Green Deal will improve the well-being and health of citizens and future generations by providing: fresh air, clean water, healthy soil and biodiversity, renovated, energy efficient buildings, healthy and affordable food, more public transport, and cleaner energy¹.

The common European Green Deal data space will interconnect currently fragmented and dispersed data from various sources (including in-situ, statistical, cartographical and remote sensing), both for/from the private and public sectors, to support the objectives of the European Green Deal. It will offer an interoperable, trusted IT environment for data processing, and a set of rules of legislative, administrative and contractual nature that determine the rights of access to and use of the data. This deliverable focuses on the in-situ data sources and its necessary components for the Green Deal Data Space.

This document is the Deliverable 2.1 for the AD4GD project. It presents the initial results achieved in the context of Task 2.1 "Identification of the in-situ networks contributing to the Green Deal data" as part of Work Package 2 "In-situ networks, CitSci and Socioeconomic Data".

The document provides an overview of the identified in-situ data sources and their relations with the Essential Variables (EVs) as a basis for a common semantic framework to better integrate heterogeneous in-situ data sources into the Green Deal Data Space (GDDS) following the FAIR principles.

The document is structured as follows:

- Section 2, enumerates the main networks of in-situ data in Europe
- Section 3, separates the different in-situ data sources contributing to the GDDS
- Section 4, proposes the Essential Variables as a common framework to semantically tag and integrate in-situ data
- Section 5, formulates recommendations for in-situ data providers
- Section 6, comments about standards and components for FAIR data in GDDS.

Net version of the document will continue this study to finally formulate a roadmap for FAIR in-situ observations for the Green Deal Data Space.

2 MAIN NETWORKS OF IN-SITU DATA IN EUROPE

The main networks of Earth Observation are recorded in the ENEON graph. Within the GEOEssential H2020 project, ENEON graph became more focused on the essential component of the in-situ measurements and networks, evolving thus into a convenient platform to analyse the Essential Variables

¹ https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal_en

in Earth observation, their relations with the in-situ networks and their role to monitor SDGs. The ENEON data model (Figure 2) defines mainly 5 classes of resources:

- A essential variable
- A essential variable product (defined by its requirements)
- A Earth Observation network (and its supporting projects)
- An SDG
- An SDG indicator

Figure 2: ENEON data model.

All 5 types of resources have several common characteristics including a unique identifier. Some resources have links to other objects by referencing their identifiers. In the UML, we model a generic LinkRef class that specializes classes (see Figure 3). In practice, the name of the subclass indicates the type of a target resource.

Figure 3: LinkRef class of ENEON data model.

This linking mechanism allows for the creation of relations in the “RDF style” and to represent all these resources as a graph (Figure 4).

Figure 4: ENEON graph.

In particular, an Earth Observation Network is one of the objects modelled in the ENEON graph (see Figure 5).

Figure 5: Detailed view of the Earth Observation Network object modelled in the ENEON graph.

A network has relations to other networks and is in charge of producing EVs. The relation between the EO network and the EV is not visible in the UML diagram because it is a backlink between the EV and the EO Network (see the section about the EVs).

In order to be useful for AD4GD, the original graph needs to be updated and extended beyond research infrastructures. Other in-situ data providers in Europe that can be relevant for the GDDS should be considered, such as INSPIRE, socioeconomic data providers, the environmental agencies and Citizen Science projects. This will be part of the WP2 activities in the next few months.

3 IN-SITU DATA SOURCE TYPES IN THE GDDS

In-situ Earth observation data can be produced by several actors, including the scientific community via the Research Infrastructures (RIs), the public administration geoportals of Member States offering socioeconomic and INSPIRE datasets, the citizen science (CitSci) initiatives generating crowdsourced information, and the more recent Internet of Things (IoT). The following sections describe the role of the aforementioned in-situ data providers in the context of the Green Deal Data Space (GDDS).

3.1 THE ROLE OF THE RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES

As defined by the Directorate-General for research and innovation of the European Commission², the term Research Infrastructures refers to “facilities that provide resources and services for research communities to conduct research and foster innovation in their fields, including [...] knowledge-related facilities such as collections, archives or scientific data infrastructures; computing systems, communication networks and any other infrastructure of a unique nature and open to external users, essential to achieve excellence in R&I; they may, where relevant, be used beyond research, for example for education or public services and they may be 'single sited', 'virtual' or 'distributed'.”

Environmental Research Infrastructures are key to provide systematic and coherent datasets needed for research addressing many aspects relevant for the European Green Deal such as: climate, natural resources, health, food security, biodiversity, and sustainable use of the marine, freshwater and soils. They target both the scientific community as well as support the environmental monitoring activities conducted by agencies across Europe. In particular, they are well positioned to give hard facts on the efficiency of the European Union and its Member States mitigation and adaptation actions.

Environmental research as a scientific domain focuses on understanding how the Earth system works at various spatial and temporal scales. Environmental research requires comprehensive observations integrated with relevant experimental and modelling approaches which are essential for understanding and predicting the Earth's environmental system functions. A federated approach to IT resources and e-science facilities is also necessary together with liable data policies compliant with the FAIR principle.

The environmental RIs already play an important role in supporting the scientific community and the society at large by³:

- generating coherent, comparable, and sustained time-series of key environmental variables;
- providing accurate large datasets and new solutions to share these data for increased scientific and technical knowledge that underpin the construction of tools supporting decision making and development of efficient regulations and policies;
- delivering essential data for more reliable communication to the public on events such as volcanic eruptions, earthquakes, poor air quality and extreme weather as well as information on biodiversity impacts;

² REGULATION (EU) 2021/695 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 28 April 2021 establishing Horizon Europe – the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation, laying down its rules for participation and dissemination, and repealing Regulations (EU) No 1290/2013 and (EU) No 1291/2013 <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32021R0695&from=EN>

³ <https://roadmap2021.esfri.eu/landscape-analysis/section-1/environment/>

- opening access to environmental big data from space-based and in-situ observations as a key driver for the development of new services and for promoting activities in the private sector.

However, a creative research beyond the traditional silos is needed to develop innovative solutions for protective and preventive measures and to identify the optimal mechanisms for their implementation.

In the geosphere, the ESFRI Landmark EPOS ERIC integrates several hundreds of individual RIs in the Solid Earth domain covering seismology, near-fault observatories, geodetic data and products, volcano observations, satellite data, geomagnetic observations, anthropogenic hazards, geological information and modelling, multi-scale laboratories, and geo-energy test-beds for low-carbon energy. Other geosciences RIs and projects are operated globally; on-going work is conducted to ensure the required coordination and integration. These include: SoWa RI for comprehensive research and understanding of soil and water ecosystems in context of sustainable landscape use and the Joint Research Centre – European Soil Data Centre (ESDAC) – Soil Atlas of Europe.

In the atmosphere, RIs includes: Long-term atmospheric observation platforms (Figure 1): the ESFRI Landmark ACTRIS; the ESFRI Landmark IAGOS (Airborne, lower atmosphere); the ESFRI Landmark ICOS ERIC; the ESFRI Landmark EISCAT_3D (upper atmosphere). International atmospheric monitoring networks in support of the European and international policies such as European Monitoring and Evaluation programme (EMEP) established in support of the Long-Range Transboundary Air Pollution (UNECE LRTAP) Convention, the Global Air Passive Sampling (GAPS) and the MONitoring NETwork (MONET) passive air monitoring programmes supporting the effectiveness evaluation of the UN Stockholm Convention on Persistent Organic Pollutants (POPs), the Global Mercury Observation System (EU project GMOS) in support of the UN Minamata Convention, Arctic Monitoring and Assessment Programme (AMAP), etc. Most of these networks were not formally established as RIs such as the IGOSP (Integrated Global Observing Systems for Persistent Pollutants) project focused on the integration of real-time monitoring data from various platforms, development of modelling tools and advanced global cyber-infrastructure for data sharing and interoperability, the Global Observation System for Mercury (GOS4M) and the Global Observation System for POPs (GOS4POP).

In the hydrosphere, much of the current science is done relying on access to existing water bodies, i.e. without specific and dedicated large-scale Research Infrastructures. The ESFRI Project DANUBIUS-RI supports interdisciplinary research in river-sea systems. It is the only physical pan-European Research Infrastructure devoted to support research on transitional zones between coastal marine and freshwater areas. The ESFRI Landmark LifeWatch ERIC as the only e-RI, extends its area of interest to the whole freshwater environment. The ESFRI Landmark AnaEE (H&F); also offers access to experimental facilities in freshwater environments, applying an ecosystem services approach to key sectors including food security, human welfare and the wider bio-economy.

In the biosphere, there are Observatories and Monitoring Facilities such as the ESFRI Landmark ICOS ERIC and the ESFRI Landmark EMBRC ERIC (H&F), related IA ASSEMBLE Plus, the ESFRI Projects DANUBIUS-RI and eLTER RI, the IAs INTERACT and JERICO-S3, SIOS (Integrating all observations, terrestrial, marine and atmosphere at Svalbard). In addition, we can find facilities for in-situ and in vivo experimentation: the ESFRI Landmark AnaEE (H&F), the IAs AQUACOSM-plus and HYDRALAB+. Some biological collections, data infrastructures and reference data exist: the ESFRI Project DiSSCo (linked IA Synthesis PLUS), the ESFRI Landmarks ELIXIR and MIRRI (H&F), and the IA BiCIKL. Finally, there are two e-Infrastructures for data, analysis and modelling: the ESFRI Landmark LifeWatch ERIC, and the IAs IS-ENES3 and SeaDataCloud. The ESFRI Project eLTER RI is tackling a broad spectrum of ecological challenges, based on observations that enable understanding ecosystems using an approach of ecological integrity, including the socio-ecological dimension. The ESFRI Landmark AnaEE (H&F) alternatively, provides experiments instead of observations, with stronger focus on agriculture and food security from a defined set of ecological and societal challenges and has a more anthropocentric approach. The ESFRI Landmark LifeWatch ERIC has a cross-domain approach and a focus on the Grand Challenges of preserving biological

diversity and of protecting ecosystem health. LifeWatch ERIC is an e-Infrastructure that enables knowledge-based solutions to environmental managers by providing access to a multitude of sets of data, services and tools about the role of biodiversity in ecosystem functioning and conservation. The focus is made in the construction and operation of Virtual Research Environments (VRE), backed by strong computational capacity and metadata catalogues. On another side, the ESFRI Landmark ICOS ERIC also has a cross-domain approach to enable understanding the carbon cycle and to provide necessary information on the land-ecosystem exchange of CO₂, CH₄ and N₂O with the atmosphere. The digitization of biological collections and the connection to genomics is a game changer in biodiversity research aiming to close the taxonomic gap, which still is a major limitation to biodiversity knowledge. The ESFRI Project DiSSCo is developing tools and resources to speed up digitization and virtual access to Natural History Collections (NHC).

In general, each RI has enough capacity to become a node in the Green Deal Data Space as contributors of observations and data of interest for the Green Deal Data Space stakeholders. Most of them are already able to share their data using standard protocols that can be adjusted for the GDDS requirements. We will review the content of the ENEON graph to update it to the Strategy report on research infrastructures roadmap 2021 released by ENFRI (see Figure 6).

Figure 6: Environmental research infrastructures included in the ESFRI roadmap 2021.

Coordinated effort of RIs across various ESFRI domains and ENV sub-domains is required to support implementation of the European Green Deal and Horizon Europe Missions (e.g. Soil Health Mission) and protect the environment, soils and biodiversity. Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS), for instance, is an important element for the long-term storage of Carbon dioxide from the atmosphere (ERA-Net ACT and the

ESFRI Landmark ECCSEL ERIC (ENE)). Green Infrastructures have been demonstrated to enhance nature protection and biodiversity beyond protected areas, to deliver ecosystem services such as climate change mitigation and re-creation, to prioritise measures for defragmentation and restoration in the agri-environment and regional development context, and to find land allocation trade-offs and possible scenarios involving all sectors.

3.2 THE ROLE OF CITIZEN SCIENCE

Citizen science is scientifically sound research conducted with the participation from members of the public (who are sometimes referred to as amateur/nonprofessional scientists). There are variations in the exact definition of citizen science, with different individuals and organisations having their own specific interpretations of what citizen science encompasses. However, many citizen science activities have a data gathering component, sometimes improving the scientific community's capacity (e.g. when a USA citizen collects observations of blossoming of trees in his garden every year and contribute these observations to the USA national phenology network) or gathering evidence of an issue citizens are sensible to and want to demonstrate and force a change (e.g. when a neighbourhood gets organised because their streets are too noisy and they want to complain to the mayor with a compelling case supported by data). In other cases, citizen activities are recorded as data by their mobile devices and wearables or by their direct interaction in social media. This data can also be crowdsourced and aggregated for purposes initially not foreseen (if conveniently authorised by them). Whatever the motivations, the value of the in-situ observations is multiplied if citizen science individual observations (voluntarily or involuntarily) are recorded using standardised protocols and are contributed to a system capable of redistributing an aggregated dataset of in-situ data that complements official sources.

There are many citizen science portals that act as aggregation facilities or data portals such as the iNaturalist for biodiversity observations, GlobeAtNight for light pollution at night, Sensor.Community for air quality monitoring. There are also citizen science knowledge hubs and platforms such as SciStarter (global coverage) and EU-Citizen.Science that provide capabilities for discovering citizen science projects. At present, SciStarter and EU-Citizen.Science platforms contain databases of 1,549 and 260 citizen science projects respectively, however neither of these platforms provide formal descriptions of or direct access or links to the data collected by these projects. EU-Citizen.Science platform offers an API to automatically extract metadata about the registered CitSci projects, yet each project needs to be inspected manually to identify what data is being collected and offered for external use.

EU-Citizen.Science platform contains 211 active projects, 32 are completed, 11 are periodically active, 4 are not yet started, and 2 are on hold (Figure 7). As shown in Figure 8, most common participation tasks are observation (60 projects), data entry (55 projects), and identification (45 projects). Note that the projects can include multiple participation tasks. Regarding project topics (Figure 9), Ecology & Environment (102 projects, 13%), Biodiversity (91 projects, 11%), and Education (64 projects, 8%) are the top three of 29 topics covered. The topics used here are of varying scale and can be aggregated, e.g. Birds, Long-term species monitoring, Insects & pollinators can all be combined under the Biodiversity theme. As with the participation tasks, the projects can also fall under multiple topics.

Figure 7: EU-Citizen.Science platform projects status.

Figure 8: EU-Citizen.Science platform participation tasks.

Figure 9: EU-Citizen.Science platform project topics.

The datasets from the citizen science aggregation portals can become interesting providers to the Green Deal Data Space. However, aggregation portals have some dynamics (some new appear every year while others are abandoned). In addition, it could be challenging for the aggregation portals to adopt the requirements for participating in the GDDS. Instead, we propose to create a reduced number of nodes that centralises the access to all citizen science datasets that can be relevant to the GDDS. We could start by setting up one node and experiment on how to implement the GDDS participation requirements.

3.3 THE ROLE OF INSPIRE AND ENVIRONMENTAL DATA

The regulation (EU) 2023/138⁴ defines in its Annex a list of specific High Value Datasets (HVD) and the arrangements for their publication and re-use in the context of the (EU) 2019/1024 Open Data Directive⁵ (formerly Public Sector Information (PSI) Directive 2003/98/EC). Also known as the Implementing Act of HVD, it mentions the geospatial, environmental and climate datasets within the scope of the INSPIRE data themes defined in Annexes I-III to Directive 2007/2/EC. INSPIRE provides ancillary data that can help give context to the environmental studies (such as elevation, sea regions), help us to interpret the spatial distribution of some environmental variables (e.g. protected areas, land use, production and industrial facilities) and other datasets that were historically collected by public administrations that help us to characterise the environment (e.g. habitats and biotopes, soil, species distribution).

In the HDV, datasets are classified in six thematic data categories. Only Geospatial and Earth Observation and environment, refers to groups of particular INSPIRE data themes. Earth Observation and environment encompasses other legislations requesting monitoring of environmental aspects such Air Quality, Water, etc. that are collected by the administration as well as for the research infrastructures as in-situ datasets. Other HDV such as Meteorological datasets and Statistical data are relevant for the GDDS.

3.4 THE ROLE OF IOT

The Internet of things (IoT) describes physical objects (or groups of such objects) with sensors, processing ability, software and other technologies that connect and exchange data with other devices and systems over the Internet or other communications networks. Traditional fields of embedded systems, wireless sensor networks, control systems, automation (including home and building automation), independently and collectively enable the Internet of things. There is a part of the IoT for the consumer market with products pertaining to the concept of the "smart home" that is out of scope of the GDDS. Smart cities use Internet of Things (IoT) sensors in urban areas to collect data and automate systems such as traffic, energy use, and waste management. While this can be laterally connected to the GDDS, we should focus on applications of IoT in in-situ environmental monitoring. In these applications, sensors detect and measure every type of environmental change in different domains such as air and water pollution (by inexpensive sensors that allow for frequent sampling), extreme weather monitoring (allows early detection and early responses to prevent loss of life and property), water safety, endangered species protection, commercial farming, and more⁶:

There are a number of concerns about the risks in the growth of IoT technologies and products, especially in the areas of privacy and security. This is particularly important when trying to integrate this kind of data in the Green Deal Data Space, as trust and privacy are fundamental elements in the data spaces.

While the IoT is a provider of in-situ, the analysis and problems of the IoT will be reported in the deliverables related to WP3.

⁴ https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg_impl/2023/138

⁵ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?qid=1561563110433&uri=CELEX:32019L1024>

⁶ https://www.tutorialspoint.com/internet_of_things/internet_of_things_environmental_monitoring.htm

4 ESSENTIAL VARIABLES AS A COMMON FRAMEWORK TO SEMANTICALLY TAG IN-SITU DATA

Essential Variables are an abstract concept that is commonly associated with a set of measurements (e.g. for the Climatic set there are the Essential Climate Variables). Each set of EVs is classified in themes (e.g. Atmosphere, Land, Ocean) and has several individual variables in it.

The Global Climate Observing System (GCOS), which was set up to ensure that the observations needed to address climate-related issues are readily available to all interested parties, specifies a total of 54 Essential Climate Variables (ECVs) of which about 60% can be addressed by satellite data and the rest of the 40% by in-situ observations. The following Figure 10 provides an overview of the GCOS Essential Climate Variables⁷.

Figure 10: GCOS Essential Climate Variables overview.

GCOS' goal is to provide comprehensive data and climate information on the total climate system. Currently, the Climate Data Store (CDS) offers free and open access to products associated with 22 ECVs. Not all the defined products have been produced so far.

⁷ <https://gcos.wmo.int/en/essential-climate-variables/table>

Figure 11: Data model used in ENEON for EVs and EV products.

The Essential Variable set used here is based on the GCOS definition but can be mapped to other EV sets and incorporates references to other EVs and to networks that measure the EV. The EV concept is extended into an EOJ that has a more detailed schema for defining EVs. EV sets can optionally be measured with one or more products as defined by GCOS, each one with a requirement class that has some generic parameters (resolutions, uncertainty, stability, etc). GEOBON (that is in charge of defining the EVs for biodiversity: EBV) also defined a very similar concept to the EV product, called “matrix” that has one extra parameter in the requirement class called “Taxonomic scope”. Figure 11 represents the data model used in ENEON for EVs and EV products.

The EV framework and its EV products provides an excellent starting point to define a set of common concepts that can be used in remote sensing as well as in in-situ data (including Citizen Science). This gives us a way to semantically classify dataset around EV products independently of the technology and technique (in-situ, remote sensing, etc.) used to capture them. In practice, this is possible if the EVs and the EVs received a global and unique identifier. One possible approach is to use a different URI for each one. However, there is community recognized ontology of EV and its products that can be used. Meanwhile the ENEON graph provides a solution for the ontology that can be used in the GDDS.

Unfortunately the EV framework is not comprehensive as some variables that might be considered non-essential will not be present. A mechanism to extend the EV or the EV products to areas that are not completely covered is needed. For example, air quality is not completely covered by ECV (in particular PM_{2.5} is not defined as a ECV product). Other more specialized vocabularies include PM_{2.5} such as <https://dd.eionet.europa.eu/vocabulary/aq/pollutant/> so we should extend the ECV if needed to cover the pilots in the project as well as the common variables in the air quality domain.

4.1 USING EV VOCABULARIES TO IDENTIFY COMPATIBLE DATASETS

By its nature, in-situ data is fragmented. Data is acquired by different local actors with different sensors at different times many times by manual or semi-automatic processes. For example, in the marine domain,

in-situ data rely on a very large number of national, regional, or global data providers. Ocean in-situ data observing networks (e.g. Argo vertical profilers, gliders, buoys or ships - research vessels and ships of opportunity) are owned or operated by a large number of institutions and agencies at national level, including, for example, national meteorological and oceanographic agencies or national research institutions⁸. A possible solution is to ensure a sustained operational flow of in-situ data into a single system by establishing interfaces with the global, regional, and coastal in-situ observing networks; a process that is called “aggregation”.

In the GDDS, data will cover different themes and variables and it should be carefully selected in order to be aggregated. If the data is not semantically tagged by the use of EV vocabularies, it will be almost impossible to be aggregated or selected as the right data as input for a numerical model in an automatic way.

4.2 USING EV VOCABULARIES IN OGC STANDARDS

Only a few of the OGC standards and APIs provide a clean way to connect data with the described EV. One of them is the Sensor Thing API (STA). STA entity data model includes the concept of observedProperty (see Figure 12) that is associated to a set of observation values through a datastream. The observedProperty represents the variable or variable product definition and includes a pointer to a URI that defines the variable being measured.

Figure 12: STA entity data model includes the concept of observedProperty.

In a STA, observations must have an observedProperty. We can enumerate all observed properties of a server by using the STA ODATA API⁹.

[https://api-samenmeten.rivm.nl/v1.0/observedProperties?\\$select=name.description](https://api-samenmeten.rivm.nl/v1.0/observedProperties?$select=name.description)

The response is as follows:

```

"value": [
  {
    "name": "pres",
    "description": "atmosferische druk"
  },
  {
    "name": "rh",

```

⁸ <https://insitu.copernicus.eu/state-of-play/copernicus-marine-environment-monitoring-service>

⁹ <https://developers.sensorup.com/docs/#queryparameters>

```

    "description": "relatieve vochtigheid"
  },
  {
    "name": "temp",
    "description": "temperatuur"
  },
  {
    "name": "nh3",
    "description": "ammoniak"
  },
  {
    "name": "no2",
    "description": "stikstofdioxide"
  },
  {
    "name": "pm25_kal",
    "description": "fijnstof gekalibreerd < 2.5microm"
  },
  {
    "name": "pm10_kal",
    "description": "fijnstof gekalibreerd < 10microm"
  },
  {
    "name": "pm25",
    "description": "fijnstof < 2.5microm"
  },
  {
    "name": "pm10",
    "description": "fijnstof < 10microm"
  }
]
}

```

Now it is possible to formulate a query that extracts only one variable (e.g. 'temp') by using its name or its definition (full URI). For example, the following query requests only the observedProperty with name equal "temp" and the request expanding all observations (in the datastream) and selects only the unitOfMeasurement the result and the phenomenonTime.

[https://api-samenmeten.rivm.nl/v1.0/observedProperties?\\$filter=name%20eq%20%27temp%27&\\$select=name,description,Datastream&\\$expand=Datastream\(\\$expand=Datastream/Observations\(\\$select=result,phenomenonTime\);\\$select=unitOfMeasurement\)](https://api-samenmeten.rivm.nl/v1.0/observedProperties?$filter=name%20eq%20%27temp%27&$select=name,description,Datastream&$expand=Datastream($expand=Datastream/Observations($select=result,phenomenonTime);$select=unitOfMeasurement))

The response is as follows:

```

{
  "value": [
    {
      "name": "temp",
      "description": "temperatuur",
      "Datastreams": [
        {
          "unitOfMeasurement": {

```

```

    "definition":
      "http://www.qudt.org/qudt/owl/1.0.0/unit/Instances.html",
      "symbol": "C"
  },
  "Observations": [
    {
      "phenomenonTime": "2023-04-14T14:00:00.000Z",
      "result": 21.76
    },
    {
      "phenomenonTime": "2023-04-14T13:00:00.000Z",
      "result": 16.4
    },
    {
      "phenomenonTime": "2023-04-14T12:00:00.000Z",
      "result": 14.41
    },
    {
      "phenomenonTime": "2023-04-14T11:00:00.000Z",
      "result": 13.8
    },
    {
      "phenomenonTime": "2023-04-14T10:00:00.000Z",
      "result": 11.7
    }
  ]
}...

```

If the Sensor Things API is used by several providers all using the same EV vocabularies it will be possible to request from all of them a single variable and create a composite dataset mixing all responses. Other OGC Web APIs lack this capacity of associating a property name with a URI defining it that is fundamental in an environmental data space. There is a need to extend the OGC Web APIs to support similar functionality.

5 RECOMMENDATIONS FOR IN-SITU DATA PROVIDERS

This section introduces what could be the steps that the in-situ data providers should take to be part of the GDDS, including the implementation of FAIR principles, their complementation with the other relevant principles (e.g., TRUST and GEO), and the role of the High Value Datasets (HVD).

5.1 FAIR PRINCIPLES

In 2016, the 'FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship' were published in Scientific Data¹⁰. The authors intended to provide guidelines to improve the Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse of digital assets. The principles emphasise machine-actionability (i.e., the capacity of computational systems to find, access, interoperate, and reuse data with none or minimal human intervention) because humans increasingly rely on computational support to deal with data as a result of the increase in volume, complexity, and creation speed of data.¹¹

¹⁰ <https://www.nature.com/articles/sdata201618>

¹¹ <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

The FAIR principles are well-known by the scientific community by the 4 words (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) that give rise to its acronym, and which are defined as follows:

- **Findable** - The first step in (re)using data is to find them. Metadata and data should be easy to find for both humans and computers. Machine-readable metadata are essential for automatic discovery of datasets and services.
- **Accessible** - Once the user finds the required data, she/he/they need to know how they can be accessed, possibly including authentication and authorisation.
- **Interoperable** - The data usually needs to be integrated with other data. In addition, the data needs to interoperate with applications or workflows for analysis, storage, and processing.
- **Reusable** - The ultimate goal of FAIR is to optimise the reuse of data. To achieve this, metadata and data should be well-described so that they can be replicated and/or combined in different settings.

However, the whole approach of FAIR consists of 10 principles, some of them with sub-principles, with a total of 15 criteria. These are the FAIR principles as defined by Go-FAIR. The detailed version of FAIR is presented in Table 1 below.

Principles Name	Principles ID	Principles Description
Findable	F1	(Meta) data are assigned globally unique and persistent identifiers
	F2	Data are described with rich metadata
	F3	Metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data they describe
	F4	(Meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource
Accessible	A1	(Meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardised communication protocol
	A1.1	The protocol is open, free and universally implementable
	A1.2	The protocol allows for an authentication and authorisation procedure where necessary
	A2	Metadata should be accessible even when the data is no longer available
Interoperable	I1	(Meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation
	I2	(Meta)data use vocabularies that follow the FAIR principles
	I3	(Meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data
Reusable	R1	(Meta)data are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes
	R1.1	(Meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage licence
	R1.2	(Meta)data are associated with detailed provenance
	R1.3	(Meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards

Table 1: Full version of the FAIR principles: Findable (F1, F2, F3, F4), Accessible (A1, A1.1, A1.2, A2), Interoperable (I1, I2, I3), and Reusable (R1, R1.1, R1.2, R1.3).

5.2 RELATION OF FAIR WITH THE GEO DMP AND TRUST

The GEO Data Management principles are 10 principles applicable to the management of all Earth Observation data products, both remote sensing and in-situ data, as well as other types of data products and services. In summary, the principles say that Earth observations should be catalogued or otherwise advertised on the internet so that they can be discovered (DMP1), and should be accessible online using open-standard encodings and services (DMP2). Data and services should be comprehensively documented

using international or community-approved standards, and to the extent possible, peer-reviewed publications, so that users can understand and make use of the data (DMP3). Metadata should include access and use conditions (DMP4), the results of quality control procedures (DMP6), and provenance statements indicating the origin and processing history of the dataset or product (DMP5). Data and associated metadata should be protected from loss (DMP7), and periodically verified to ensure integrity, authenticity and readability (DMP8). Corrections and updates to data and metadata records should be performed as required (DMP9). Finally, persistent identifiers should be assigned to data so that they can be tracked and cited and data providers can be acknowledged (DMP10)¹². There is an overlap with the FAIR principles that will be addressed by the GEO DMP subgroup in the near future. The FAIR principles are complemented by the TRUST Principles. The TRUST Principles are a set of guidelines to demonstrate trustworthiness in digital repositories defined by the digital repository community. Transparency, Responsibility, User focus, Sustainability, and Technology are the five TRUST Principles. Together they provide a common framework to facilitate discussion around implementing best practices in the area of digital preservation (so they overlap with the DMP7 DMP8 and DMP9). The following Figure 13 represents the correspondence between the GEO DMP and the FAIR and TRUST principles.

Figure 13: Correspondence between the GEO DMP and the FAIR and TRUST principles.

5.3 IMPLEMENTING FAIR PRINCIPLES

In order to facilitate and promote the implementation of the FAIR principles, the European Commission expert group on FAIR data published the report “Turning FAIR into reality”¹³. This report analyses what is needed to implement FAIR and provides an Action Plan with concrete recommendations and actions for stakeholders for advancing in Open Science.

¹² https://www.earthobservations.org/documents/dswg/201504_data_management_principles_condensed_final.pdf

¹³ <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/7769a148-f1f6-11e8-9982-01aa75ed71a1/language-en/format-PDF/source-80611283>

A total of twenty-seven recommendations are drawn, grouped into Priority Recommendations and Supporting Recommendations. Fifteen Priority Recommendations are made. These relate to the key concepts of FAIR Digital Objects, which are then implemented through interoperability frameworks. The whole set of recommendations is presented as follows.

■ PRIORITY RECOMMENDATIONS

Step 1: Define – concepts for FAIR Digital Objects and the ecosystem

- Rec. 1: Define FAIR for implementation
- Rec. 2: Implement a model for FAIR Digital Objects
- Rec. 3: Develop components of a FAIR ecosystem

Step 2: Implement – culture, technology and skills for FAIR practice

- Rec. 4: Develop interoperability frameworks for FAIR sharing within disciplines and for interdisciplinary research
- Rec. 5: Ensure Data Management via Data Management Plans
- Rec. 6: Recognise and reward FAIR data and data stewardship
- Rec. 7: Support semantic technologies
- Rec. 8: Facilitate automated processing
- Rec. 9: Develop assessment frameworks to certify FAIR services
- Rec. 10: Professionalise data science and data stewardship roles and train researchers
- Rec. 11: Implement curriculum frameworks and training

Step 3: Embed and sustain – incentives, metrics and investment

- Rec. 12: Develop metrics for FAIR Digital Objects
- Rec. 13: Develop metrics to certify FAIR services
- Rec. 14: Provide strategic and coordinated funding
- Rec. 15: Provide sustainable funding

■ SUPPORTING RECOMMENDATIONS

- Rec. 16: Apply FAIR broadly
- Rec. 17: Align and harmonise FAIR and Open data policy
- Rec. 18: Cost data management
- Rec. 19: Select and prioritise FAIR Digital Objects
- Rec. 20: Deposit in Trusted Digital Repositories
- Rec. 21: Encourage and incentivise reuse of FAIR outputs
- Rec. 22: Use information held in Data Management Plans
- Rec. 23: Develop FAIR components to meet research needs
- Rec. 24: Incentivise research infrastructures and other services to support FAIR data
- Rec. 25: Implement FAIR metrics to monitor uptake
- Rec. 26: Support data citation and next generation metrics
- Rec. 27: Open EOSC to all providers but ensure services are FAIR

6 STANDARDS AND COMPONENTS FOR FAIR DATA IN GDDS

6.1 STANDARDS AND COMPONENTS FOR FINDING IN-SITU DATA IN THE GDDS

While most people rely on Google to find textual information, finding data is more complex. Since most datasets are just sequences of numbers they have almost no meaning and they cannot be indexed without metadata. Metadata is composed of textual descriptions of the data. Formal standards for geospatial environmental data metadata are Dublin Core and ISO 19115 and DCAT. Individual metadata records are stored in metadata catalogues that are indexed databases that allow for querying the metadata and

retrieving entries that match with the requested characteristics such as topic, spatial extent, temporal extent, resolution and data quality indicators. Common metadata catalogues are STAC, OGC CSW and CKAN. Another way to improve findability is to associate each and every dataset with a resolvable and permanent identifier (PID). A reference of the dataset PID in a report or in scientific literature will make the dataset immediately findable. One of the main difficulties in geospatial information is that it is structured in long temporal and spatial dataset series sometimes resulting in flooding the results with a lot of similar results. Another problem in geospatial information is the almost absence of criteria to prioritise or rank the results. The use of Geospatial User Feedback (GUF) can help in ranking the results and providing additional information to users based on previous experiences using the same dataset.

It is expected that the GDDS will have one or more nodes that will be dedicated to data discovery and finding information.

6.2 STANDARD AND COMPONENTS FOR IN-SITU DATA ACCESS IN THE GDDS

One of the main problems of geospatial information is the variety of formats and data models of the geospatial information. However, there are 3 main data models that results in a number of standards:

- Data can be a continuous coverage represented by a raster file, a data cube, a point cloud or a TIN data structure. In this case, the OGC Web Coverage Service and the OGC API Coverages are two standards for data access of a subset of the coverage data.
- Data can also be a collection of sparse points, lines or polygons representing geospatial features on the ground. In this case, the OGC Web Feature Service and the OGC API Features are two standards for data access of a subset of the feature data collections.
- Data can also be sets of observations done by sensors over the terrain. The OGC Sensor Observation Service and the OGC Sensor Things API are two standards for data access of a subset of the observations and measurements

There are also standards that focus on geospatial queries in a way that are agnostic of the data model such as the OGC Environmental Data Retrieval.

The separation of the metadata in catalogues and the data in access services has one main issue. Sometimes the data provider discontinues the product or moves it to another URL without notifying the catalogue about the change. A user search finds hits that will never give access to the disconnected data. In an environment such as the GDDS, this will not only generate frustration but also lack of trust on the data space.

Most of these services are maintained by the data providers themselves so each provider will have a node in the GDDS. The citizen science data could be an exception to this, as discussed in previous sections.

6.3 STANDARD FOR IN-SITU DATA (SEMANTIC) INTEROPERABILITY IN THE GDDS

Traditionally geospatial information data models and formats cared about the description of the geographic properties and assumed that the thematic component of the information was somehow solved. One of the main examples of this is the GML. The long document describing GML 2.0 defines how to encode geographical features in XML objects. To do so, it defines XML schemas (XSD) for geographic objects (e.g. points, lines, polygons). To define your geospatial features you are supposed to define a class in an XSD with thematic properties and geographical properties. While in XSD you can define a property type you can not add units of measure or attach a variable description (e.g. an EV product name or URI concept definition). The syntax of XSD is too restrictive. A similar situation happens with a Shapefile where the thematic properties are described in DBF tables only by up to 10 character column name. Metadata describing the data model could fix this but it does not. For example, ISO19110 Feature Catalogue (see

Figure 14) incorporates valueMeasurementUnit (to add a unit of measure) and valueType (if it is Integer or String, etc).

Figure 14: Detailed view of the ISO19110 Feature Catalogue model.

Using the FC_PropertyType and extending "definition" to include a URI as well as a name (as explained by ISO19139) could be done (see Figure 15). Unfortunately, the ISO19110 is rarely used and this level of detail is difficult to see in Feature services.

Figure 15: How to extend CharacterString to include a URI.

The ISO 19115-1 fixes this only for coverages incorporating a "name" in MD_RangeDimension (that is a MD_identifier that e.g. allows pointing to a vocabulary of variables) and units in the MD_SampleDimension (Figure 16). Unfortunately, coverage services do not usually provide coverage data accompanied by ISO 19115-1 records and if they do, it rarely includes this level of detail.

Figure 16: Description of the Range types included as values in a coverage following the ISO 19115-1.

As we have said before, the Sensor Things API is almost the only data access standard that has a mandatory observedProperty defined by a URI.

But having data access services that are capable of linking to external vocabularies is not going to fix the problem if there is no common vocabulary to link with. That is why the OGC definition service is proposed as a vocabulary repository for observedProperties. In our opinion it should contain a list of EV and its products and other extended vocabularies of variables that we could reuse and point from the data that is being included in the data space.

Another component of interoperability and trust is the need for describing the provenance and the data quality of the data. These aspects are reasonably covered by the ISO 19115-1 and the ISO19157 standards respectively.

6.4 AUTHENTICATION AND PRIVACY ASPECTS

While most of the data in the Green Deal data space should remain open, it could be good to have controlled access to sensitive data and private data when needed. Standards for SSO such as OpenID Connect can be used. The Authenix service developed and tested in the Cos4Cloud project is a possible solution (<https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/authenix>). Another issue in the GDDS is the need for trust in the data and the services. Certificates and HTTPS can be used to ensure that services are genuine and have not been tampered with. We should adopt solutions coming from IT mainstream

7 CONCLUSIONS

A draft architecture for the GDDS data space shall be composed by International Data Spaces Association for authentication authorization, certification and logging proposals but complemented by geospatial and environmental APIs (or equivalent web services) such as data discovery CSW catalogues (or OGC API records), a OGC Web Coverage Service (and the OGC API Coverages) for sharing coverage data a OGC Web Feature Service (and the OGC API Features) for sharing feature data, a the OGC Sensor Observation Service (or a OGC Sensor Things API) for sharing observations data, a WMS/WMTS (or a OGC API maps and tiles)

for data visualisation and a WPS (or an OGC API processes) for data processing. A definition service is proposed as a vocabulary repository for observed properties containing a list of EV and its products and other extended vocabularies of variables that we could reuse and point from the data. Most of these services are maintained by the data providers themselves so each provider will have a node in the GDDS, as represented in the following Figure 17:

Figure 17: Draft architecture combining IDSA general IT concept with our views on Geospatial components.

The initial results presented in this document will be worked on and extended in the Deliverable 2.2 with a set of recommendations for the GDDS in-situ component to be released in month 20 of the project.